

A Study on Sectorwise Composition of FDI Inflows in India

OPEN ACCESS

Volume: 7

Special Issue: 1

Month: August

Year: 2019

P-ISSN: 2320-4168

E-ISSN: 2582-0729

Impact Factor: 4.118

Citation:

Jaishankar, D., and
Kalaiselvi Sivaraman.
“A Study on Sectorwise
Composition of FDI
Inflows in India.”
*Shanlax International
Journal of Commerce*,
vol. 7, no. S1, 2019,
pp. 72-78.

DOI:

[https://doi.org/10.5281/
zenodo.3451613](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3451613)

D. Jaishankar

*Research Scholar, University of Madras & Associate Professor
Dr. Ambedkar Law University, Chennai*

Dr. Kalaiselvi Sivaraman

*Research Supervisor & Associate Professor
University of Madras, Chennai*

Abstract

Since the beginning of economic reforms in 1991, major reforms initiatives have been taken in the fields of investment, trade, financial sector, exchange control simplification of procedures, enactment of competition and amendments in the intellectual property rights laws, etc. India provides a liberal, attractive, and investor friendly investment climate. India has the most liberal and transparent policies on FDI among the emerging economies. Foreign direct investment (FDI) up to 100 percent is allowed under the automatic route in most of activities/sectors. FDI in sectors/activities to the extent permitted under automatic route does not require any prior approval either by the Government or RBI. The investors are only required to notify the Regional office within 30 days of receipt of inward remittances and file the required documents in that office within 30 days of issue of shares to foreign investors. On the other hands other sectors are required the approval by either the foreign investment promotion board or the cabinet committee of foreign. Presently foreign direct investment is freely allowed in most of the sectors but a few sectors where the existing and notified sectoral policy does not permit foreign direct investment beyond a specific limit. Foreign direct investment for almost all sectors/ activities can be brought in through the automatic route under the power delegated to the Reserve bank of India and the remaining sectors/ activities through government approval. This research article brings forth the data related to centre government approved foreign direct investment in these sectors on the recommendations of the foreign investment promotion board (FIPB).

Keywords: Service Sector, Construction Development, Computer Software and Hardware, Telecommunications, Drugs and Pharmaceuticals, Automobile Industry, Chemicals Sector, Trading Sector, Power Sector and Hotel & Tourism.

Introduction

One outstanding feature of the present-day world has been the circulation of private capital flows in the form of foreign direct investment (FDI) in developing countries, especially since 1990s. Since the 1980s, the multinational corporations (MNCs) have come out as major actors in the globalization context. In this context, globalization offers a parallel opportunity for developing countries like India to attain quicker economic growth through trade and

investment. In the period 1970s, international trade grew more rapidly than FDI, so far that international trade was most significant economic activities for international collaboration. This situation changed fundamentally in the middle of the 1980s, when FDI started to increase sharply. In this period, the FDI has increased its importance by transferring technologies and establishing marketing and procuring networks for efficient production and sales internationally.

Conceptual Framework of FDI

Capital is stated as the engine of growth. This statement has gained more importance in the recent times. Traditionally, the various sources of capital for developing countries were either the demand of their output (raw material) by industrial countries or foreign aid and or loan from foreign banks. However, now-a-days, the official development assistance flows are steadily declining. Beside others, FDI as a source of funds has gained very high importance, in recent years. FDI is an investment involving a long-term relationship and reflecting a lasting interest and control of a resident entity in one economy. FDI involves the ownership and control of a foreign company in foreign country. In exchange for this ownership the investing country usually transfers some of its financial, technical, managerial, trademark and other resources to the recipient country. The govt of India in March 2008 revised the definition in line with international practices. The revised FDI data includes equity capital including that of un-incorporated entities, non cash acquisition against technology transfer, plant and machinery, goodwill, business development, control premium, and non- competition fees. It also includes reinvested earning including that of incorporated entities, unincorporated entities and reinvested earnings of indirectly held direct investment enterprises.

Current Scenario of FDI Inflow in India

Since economic reforms initiated in 1991, Government of India has taken many programs to magnetize FDI inflows to improve the Indian economy. An important objective of promoting FDI in India and other developing countries has been to promote efficiency in production and increase exports. However, any increase in equity stake of the foreign investors in existing joint ventures or purchase of a share of equity by them in domestic firms would not automatically change the direction of the firm. That is “the aim of FDI investors would be to benefit from the profit earned in the Indian market. As, a result, in such cases FDI inflows need not be accompanied by any substantial increase in exports, whether such investment leads to modernization of domestic capacity or not”. Therefore, it is a challenge for a developing country like India to channelize its capital inflow through FDI into a potential source of productivity gain for domestic firms.

The Entry Routes For FDI in India

Prior to 1991, all FDI proposals were approved on a case by case basis with a 40% total foreign equity participation cap. Since July, 1991 India has significantly liberalised its foreign investment policy. As per the rules, policies and procedures of liberalisation, FDI comes through four routes in India as follows:

RBI (Automatic Route)

This route was introduced to facilitate FDI inflows. Foreign investment in an Indian entity does not require prior government approval in this route. Companies proposing foreign investment under this route can issue shares up to the limit of foreign equity capital prescribed or the foreign investors. Remittances can also be received for same. The reporting period for this purpose to the RBI is 30 days. Approval is automatic is sixty categories of industries.

Government (SIA/FIPB)

Route are Non-Automatic route, the schemes which are non-automatic in nature are referred to FIPB. In the organisational structure, industry secretary is the chairman of FIPB. The other members are finance secretary, commerce secretary and secretary (economic relations), ministry of external affairs. This apex board gives clearance on a case by case basis. Such cases include sectors that require industrial licenses, foreign investment exceeding 24% of equity in small scale industries, foreign investment where the foreign interest has an existing venture in some field India, and all proposals falling outside the predetermined sectoral caps or in sectors where FDI is usually not permitted but authorised in certain cases at the discretion of GOI. FIPB gives clearance after consulting the concerned ministries and considering the size of investment. Normal processing time is four to six weeks. FIPB adopts liberal approach for all sectors and all types of proposals. The rejections are almost negligible. SIA assists FIIA while processing FDI Proposals FIPA (Foreign Investment Implementation Authority) assist foreign investors which have got central government approval in clearance of state level problems.

A Non- Resident is an individual who is either a citizen of India or a person of Indian origin but also who is not 'resident' in India. NRIs also include companies, partnership firms, trusts, societies and corporate bodies where 60% of the equity is owned by the NRIs. There is a sizable population of Indians living outside. Indian government offers various opportunities to attract surplus funds of NRIs. They can deposit in India through banks accounts like non-resident external rupee account NRI, foreign currency non-resident (Bank) account FCNR(S) and Non-Resident ordinary Rupee (NRO) account.

Acquisition of Share

Acquisition route has been introduced since January, 1996. This was included as a part of FDI under section 29 of the FERA (foreign exchange regulation act), 1973, now it comes under section 5 of FEMA (foreign exchange management act) 1999. According to new provisions of FEMA, the proposals for FDI involving acquisition of share in already existing companies are considered only if application made by Indian company or related proposal is supported by board resolution of Indian company.

Research Methodology

After the data have been collected from secondary sources, research turns to the task of analyses and interpretation. The data have been arranged properly on annual basis and then inferences have been drawn. Statistical tools like Percentage share out of Total FDI, Growth rate percentage, and compound growth rate has been calculated in order to draw proper inference and analysis.

FDI in Services Sector

The services sector in India has remained the most vibrant sector in terms of contribution to national and state incomes, trade flows, FDI inflows and employment. There is a new wave in the growth of India financial sector after liberalisation insurance industry growing with rapid rate. The number of merger and acquisition in the insurance industry as well as in banking sector also, number of private banks are growing in India. The service sector Includes Financial, Banking services, Insurance services, Non-financial and Business services, Outsourcing, Research & Development, Courier, Technical Testing and Analysis, Commodity Exchange, etc. The FDI inflow in service sector has been given in Table 1 from the year 2000 to 2018. The inflow of FDI has been increased from 11455.83 million in 2004 to 6,39,090.00 million in 2018. Initially, the pace of growth of FDI in service sector was slow. However, the flow of FDI in service sector increased significantly

after the year 2015 despite huge fluctuation from year to year. The inflow of FDI in service sector reached at top level in the year 2018 with 6,39,090.00 million. However, we have discussed growth over the preceding year i.e. 504 percentage in 2006, 136.11 percent in 2008 and 128.40 percent in 2015. But some time it has been observed declining growth over the previous year i.e. -46.10 percent in 2013, followed by -25.71 percent in 2017.

Table 1 FDI Inflows in Service Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Service Sector	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	1861.5	104411	1.78	-
2001	8202.24	160711	5.1	340.63
2002	15431.39	161345	9.56	88.14
2003	13903.59	95640	14.54	-9.9
2004	11455.83	147814	7.75	-17.61
2005	28,961.35	192707	15.03	152.81
2006	1,75,019.53	503573	34.76	504.32
2007	1,43,776.22	654950	21.95	-17.85
2008	3,39,475.12	1595295	21.28	136.11
2009	2,72,429.50	1309799	20.8	-19.75
2010	1,61,538.68	960150	16.82	-40.7
2011	2,38,886.13	1599349	14.94	47.88
2012	2,52,619.24	1215914	20.78	5.75
2013	1,36,161.47	1294825	10.52	-46.1
2014	1,79,500.90	1753134	10.24	31.83
2015	4,09,974.58	2525614	16.23	128.4
2016	5,82,140.00	3116440	18.67	41.99
2017	4,32,490.00	2827680	15.29	-25.71
2018	6,39,090.00	2888885	22.12	47.77
Total	4042917.27	231,08,236	17.50	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

The FDI inflow in service sector ranged from 1.78 percent in 2000 to 22.12 percent in 2018 of total FDI during the study period. The share of FDI declined in the six years after reaching at peak level in the year 2006 and was 10.24 percent of total FDI in 2014.

FDI in Construction Development

The FDI in real estate/construction development has been permitted since 2005. It is subject to some restriction like development of minimum area, minimum capitalization, investment lock in, restriction on FDI in residential plots, restriction on transfer of shares, etc. These conditions could be met only by the big industry players. But the Government of India (GOI) amended the foreign direct investment (FDI) policy in Construction Development sector on 3rd December, 2014 by relaxing some conditions. These relates to reduction in minimum floor area, development of project, relaxation within 5 years of obtaining all in minimum investment and no need of completion certificate. Similarly, the Projects committing at least 30% project cost for affordable housing are exempt from Minimum area and Minimum capitalization requirements.

**Table 2 FDI Inflows in Construction Sector with Percentage Share
out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018**

Year	FDI in Construction Sector	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2004	6419.88	147814	4.34	-
2005	5118.03	192707	2.66	-20.28
2006	36613.91	503573	7.27	615.39
2007	51924.4	654950	7.93	41.82
2008	103623.52	1595295	6.5	99.57
2009	116954.93	1309799	8.93	12.87
2010	71110.5	960150	7.41	-39.2
2011	84982.5	1599349	5.31	19.51
2012	127191.56	1215914	10.46	49.67
2013	69207.87	1294825	5.34	-45.59
2014	61835.69	1753134	3.53	-10.65
2015	10,609.99	2525614	0.42	-82.84
2016	7,030.00	3116440	0.22	-33.74
2017	3,472.00	2827680	0.12	-50.61
2018	15,030.00	2888885	0.52	332.89
Total	7,71,124.78	225,86,129.00	3.41	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

The FDI inflow in construction development sector includes the FDI inflow for the construction of townships, housing and built-up infrastructure in the country. The sector wise break up of cumulative FDI inflow shows that the construction development has been placed next to after service sector. The FDI inflow in this sector in the country from 2004 to 2018 has been given in Table 2. There has been significant increase in the gross total inflow of FDI in construction sector from 6419.88 million in the year 2004 to 15,030.00 million in the year 2018. There has been heavy fluctuation in FDI flow during this period. FDI in construction development sector reached at peak level in the year 2012. Subsequently, it declined substantially and it was merely Rs. 3,472 million in the year 2017. The share of FDI in construction development ranged merely from 0.52 percent in the year 2018 to 10.46 percent in the year 2012 of the total FDI.

FDI in Computer Software and Hardware

The internationalisation of computer software and hardware services activity came late as compared with the manufacturing industry and many other service activities. Only hardware manufacturers served international markets in the period up to the mid1970s. However, by the end of the 1980s, the international spread in the coverage of this industry had taken off. Packaged software was becoming more readily available and exported; more specialist systems and software houses were expanding and were soon followed by the major IT service outsourcing companies, for example EDS and Cap Gemini Sogeti. This was in turn replaced by the rise of more complete computer software and services “majors”, such as United States based Microsoft and Oracle Corporations. The Information Technology (IT) industry has shaped up as a major success story in India’s economy.

Table 3 FDI Inflows in Computer Software and Hardware Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Software & Hardware Sector	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	12008.32	104411	11.5	
2001	20566.93	160711	12.8	71.27
2002	31908.64	161345	19.8	55.15
2003	13550.09	95640	14.2	-57.53
2004	31,030.11	147814	21	129
2005	42,066.76	192707	21.8	35.57
2006	87,492.90	503573	17.4	107.99
2007	1,02,148.54	654950	15.6	16.75
2008	78,102.50	1595295	4.9	-23.54
2009	32,124.70	1309799	2.5	-58.87
2010	45,347.95	960150	4.7	41.16
2011	31,350.97	1599349	2	-30.87
2012	34,374.34	1215914	2.8	9.64
2013	36,598.31	1294825	2.8	6.47
2014	95,622.02	1753134	5.5	161.27
2015	425370.39	2525614	16.8	344.85
2016	24,605	3116440	0.7	-94.22
2017	39,670	2827680	1.4	61.23
2018	45,297	2888885	1.5	14.18
Total	12,29,235.47	231,08,236.00	5.32	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

The FDI inflow in computer software and hardware has been given in Table 3. Its gross total inflow increased from Rs. 31,030.11 million in the year 2004 to Rs. 4, 25,370.39 million in the year, 2015, but gradually decreased thereafter. The volume of FDI inflow in this sector increased from Rs.31030.11 million in 2004 to Rs. 102148.54 million in 2007, but its share in total inflow of FDI declined from 21 percent in 2004 to 15.6 percent in 2007. Further, it declined to Rs. 31350.95 million (2 percent) in 2011. Thereafter, FDI in this sector rose constantly and reached to Rs. 425370.39 million (16.8 percent) in 2015 and decreased in the year 2016 to the extent of Rs. 24605 million (0.7 percent) and then increased gradually from 2017 to the extent of Rs. 39670 million.

The share of FDI inflow in computer software and hardware was lies between 21.0 to 15.6 percent of total FDI inflow during the years 2004 to 2007. Therefore, it declined and its share in total FDI inflow decreased from 2 to 5.5 percent from 2008 to 2014. In the end of 2015, it increased significantly and its share increased with 16.8 percent of the total inflow. Further the share in total FDI inflow decreased after 2015.

FDI in Telecommunications

The Telecom industry has witnessed significant growth in subscriber base over the last decade, with increasing network coverage and a competition induced decline in tariffs acting as catalysts for the growth in subscriber base. Liberalisation of the sector has not only led to rapid growth but

also helped a great deal towards maximization of consumer benefits. Telecom sector has witnessed a continuous rising trend in the total number of telephone subscribers. The number of telephone subscribers in India increased from 1,022.61 million at the end of September, 2015 to 1,036.41 million at the end of December, 2015. The overall Tele density in India increased to 81.83 as on 31December, 2015. Subscription in Urban Areas increased 600.66 million at the end of December, 2015, whereas rural subscription increased 435.75 million. Total number of Internet subscribers has increased to 324.95 million September, 2015.8. However, the Indian telecom network is the second largest in the world after China. With the adoption of liberal policy in telecom sector, it could attract more FDI.

Table 4 FDI Inflows in Telecommunication Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Telecommunication Sector	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	6855.41	104411	6.57	-
2001	42,671.49	1,60,711.00	26.55	522.45
2002	9,090.70	1,61,345.00	5.63	-78.7
2003	7272.59	95,640.00	7.6	-20
2004	6,004.37	147814	4.06	-17.44
2005	9,639.13	192707	5	60.54
2006	41,702.15	503573	8.28	332.63
2007	43,541.50	654950	6.65	4.41
2008	1,15,954.81	1595295	7.27	166.31
2009	1,23,729.71	1309799	9.45	6.71
2010	69,144.60	960150	7.2	-44.12
2011	1,04,926.19	1599349	6.56	51.75
2012	4,293.12	1215914	0.35	-95.91
2013	17,700.03	1294825	1.37	312.29
2014	2,34,555.11	1753134	13.38	1225.17
2015	83,373.33	2525614	3.3	-64.45
2016	37,435.00	3116440	1.2	-55.10
2017	39,748.00	2827680	1.4	6.18
2018	18,337.00	2888885	0.63	-53.87
Total	10,15,974.24	231,08,236.00	4.40	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

The Telecommunication sector includes telecommunications, radio paging, cellular mobile, basic telephone services etc. The country wise break up of cumulative FDI inflow shows that the telecommunication has been placed at fourth place after the computer software and hardware. The FDI inflow in telecommunication sector has been given in Table 4 from 2000 to 2018. There has been wide fluctuation in FDI flow in telecommunication sector. The gross total inflow increased from 6855.41 million in the year 2000 to 18337 million in the year 2018. The flow of FDI in telecommunication was moving at slow pace up to the year 2007 and constituted a small part of total

inflow. However, it sharply increased to 115,954.81 million in 2008, 123729.71 million in 2009 and 2,34,555 in the year 2014. However, declined in next year and was merely 83,373.33 million in 2015. However, it increased to 234555.11 million in 2014. There has been heavy fluctuation of FDI inflows in this sector from year to year.

As result the share of FDI inflow in telecommunication sector as compared to total FDI inflow ranged from 0.35 percent in 2012 to maximum 26.55 percent in 2001 during this period. However, it remained between 6 to 7 percent most of the years during this period. To sum up, telecommunication has become important destination of FDI flow to India.

FDI in Drugs and Pharmaceuticals

The Indian Pharmaceutical industry has achieved an eminent global position in pharma sector and has been witnessing phenomenal growth in recent years. It is well known that India is emerging as a world leader in generic pharmaceuticals production, supplying 20% of the global market for generic medicines. The industry accounts for 8% of global production, and is exporting to over 200 countries. India is a major vaccine producer and has 18 major vaccine manufacturing facilities. These vaccines are used for the national and international market (150 countries) which makes India a major vaccine supplier across the globe.

Table 5 FDI Inflows in Drugs and Pharmaceutical Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Drugs and Pharmaceutical Sector	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	2079.88	104411	1.99	-
2001	4081.79	1,60,711.00	2.54	96.25
2002	2510.52	1,61,345.00	1.56	-38.49
2003	2793.28	95,640.00	2.92	11.26
2004	15711.08	147814	10.63	462.46
2005	5107.25	192707	2.65	-67.49
2006	9757.29	503573	1.94	91.05
2007	11405.68	654950	1.74	16.89
2008	11085.87	1595295	0.69	-2.8
2009	9794.75	1309799	0.75	-11.65
2010	10039.65	960150	1.05	2.5
2011	145314.8	1599349	9.09	1347.41
2012	33117.16	1215914	2.72	-77.21
2013	100054.57	1294825	7.73	202.12
2014	73763.98	1753134	4.21	-26.28
2015	40,268.56	2525614	1.59	-45.41
2016	5,723.00	3116440	0.18	-85.79
2017	6,502.00	2827680	0.22	13.61
2018	1,842.00	2888885	0.06	-71.67
Total	4,90,953.11	231,08,236.00	2.12	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

As western markets mature there has been a prominent shift in focus towards emerging markets like India. The Indian pharmaceutical industry is ranked 3rd in the world in terms of production volume and 13th in domestic consumption volume. It is one of the leading drug industries of developing countries. Over a period of three decades, India’s pharmaceutical industry has evolved into a world leader in the production of high-quality generic drugs. The 100% foreign direct investment (FDI) is allowed in Greenfield investment under automatic route in the drugs and pharmaceuticals sector, including those involving use of recombinant technology. Also, FDI up to 100% is permitted for Brownfield investments (i.e. investments in existing companies), in the pharmaceuticals sector, under the Government approval route.

The sector wise break up of cumulative FDI inflows shows that the drugs and pharmaceutical has been placed fifth after telecommunication. The break-up of FDI inflow in this sector from 2000 to 2018 has been given in Table 5. The FDI inflow in drugs and pharmaceutical sector has been increased from 2079.88 million in the year 2000 to 40268.56 million in the year 2015 and decreased in the year 2018 to the extent of 1,842 million. The share of FDI inflow in drugs and pharmaceutical sector ranged between 1.99 percent in 2000 to 10.63 percent in 2004. Further, it has been declined and reached 0.06 percent in 2018. However, it has been increased with 9.09 percent in 2011.

FDI in Automobile Industry

The Indian automotive industry has come a long way from its nascent state at the time of India’s independence. At the time of 1950 the automobile production was 4,000 vehicles whereas now it crossed the historic landmark of 20.7 million vehicles in 2013. Until 1983 the Indian automotive segment was a closed market with limited players such as Hindustan Motors, Premier, Telco, Ashok Leyland, and Mahindra & Mahindra. Therefore, the growth of the market was limited by supply and most of the cars were outdated models compared to neighbouring countries. During the time of 1983–1993 joint venture concept was evolved through relaxation of Indian policies on foreign investments. This period was really very helpful to India for learning technology from foreign companies. In the liberalisation period automotive industry improved in various aspects such as technological, infrastructural, production and delivery. Foreign investment has a significant influence on the Indian automotive industry as we see it today. Although the Indian automotive industry has its genesis in the 40’s it has seen considerable growth in the last two decades mainly due to economic liberalisation including 100% FDI in this sector. Global auto and component manufacturing companies are motivated to establish manufacturing and R&D facilities in the country due to availability of large pool of skilled workers, low production costs, faster design and development process and emerging market status. Presently, there are more than 30 OEMs offering more than 75 options in all categories of vehicles. India’s automotive industry is the world’s sixth largest producer of automobiles in terms of volume and value and has grown 14.4% in the last decade.

Table 6 FDI Inflows in Drugs and Pharmaceutical Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Automobile Industry Sector	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	12,180.28	1,04,411	11.67	-
2001	13,820.05	1,60,711	8.6	13.46
2002	21,242.48	1,61,345	13.17	53.71

2003	15,133.84	95,640	15.82	-28.76
2004	6,342.54	1,47,814	4.29	-58.09
2005	5,892.16	1,92,707	3.06	-7.1
2006	11,773.53	5,03,573	2.34	99.82
2007	14,895.00	6,54,950	2.27	26.51
2008	48,094.92	15,95,295	3.01	222.89
2009	67,282.36	13,09,799	5.14	39.89
2010	56,598.50	9,60,150	5.89	-15.88
2011	39,266.69	15,99,349	2.46	-30.62
2012	59,797.67	12,15,914	4.92	52.29
2013	90,020.28	12,94,825	6.95	50.54
2014	1,36,349.52	17,53,134	7.78	51.47
2015	1,85,207.61	25,25,614	7.33	35.83
2016	10,824.00	3116440	0.34	-94.16
2017	13,461.00	2827680	0.47	24.36
2018	18,309.00	2888885	0.63	36.02
Total	8,26,491.43	231,08,236.00	3.58	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

The sector wise break up of FDI inflow shows that the automobile industry has been at sixth place after drugs and pharmaceutical industry. The inflow of FDI in this sector from 2000 to 2018 has been given in Table 6. Its gross total inflow increased from 12180.28 million in the year 2000 to 185207.61 million in the year 2015 and then decreased thereafter. The flow of FDI in automobile industry was moving at slow pace up to the year 2007 and constituted a small part of total inflow. There has been significant increase in FDI flow after 2007 in automobile sector, particularly, during the last three years i.e. 2013 to 2015. The share of FDI inflow in this sector ranged between 2.27 percent to 15.82 percent during this period. Initially, the aggregate flow of FDI in India was relatively low and as a result the share of FDI in automobile industry was relatively high and ranged between 3.06 percent to 15.82 percent. After the year 2005, the aggregate FDI flow to India increased significantly and the share of FDI in automobile industry declined despite significantly increased in absolute amount. However, the share of FDI flow in this sector has been rising since 2012.

FDI in Chemicals (Other Than Fertilizers) Sector

The chemical sector has witnessed growth of 13-14% in the last 5 years while petrochemicals have registered a growth of 8-9% over the same period. The chemicals industry in India is the largest consumer of its own products, consuming 33% of its output. The Indian chemicals industry has a diversified manufacturing base that produces world-class products. Chemicals constitute 5.4% of India's total exports. India already has a strong presence in the export market in the sub-segments of dyes, pharmaceuticals and agro chemicals. India exports dyes to Germany, the UK, the US, Switzerland, Spain, Turkey, Singapore and Japan. Government recognizes Chemical industry as a key growth element of Indian economy. In terms of volume of production of chemicals, India is positioned as the third largest producer in Asia, next to China and Japan, and the 12th largest in the world. It contributes around 5% to India's total GDP. The chemical industry also accounts for

13% share in total exports and 8% share in total imports of India. The sector contributes around 20% to national revenue by way of taxes and levies. The Indian government allows 100% FDI in the chemicals sector. No licenses are required for production of most of the chemicals, including organic, inorganic, dyestuff and pesticides. Only a few hazardous chemicals need licenses for production. The government is setting up port-based chemicals parks in existing and new SEZs to encourage clustering, provide infrastructure and enable tax concessions. This will provide a further boost to the chemicals industry.

Table 7 FDI Inflows in Chemicals (Other than Fertilizers) Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Chemicals (Other Than Fertilizers)	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	5380.66	104411	5.15	
2001	2952.1	160711	1.84	-45.13
2002	5799.58	161345	3.59	96.46
2003	2849.05	95640	2.98	-50.87
2004	8677.14	147814	5.87	204.56
2005	6562.53	192707	3.41	-24.37
2006	17944.83	503573	3.56	173.44
2007	10170.23	654950	1.55	-43.33
2008	26360.71	1595295	1.65	159.19
2009	22113.47	1309799	1.69	-16.11
2010	20450.74	960150	2.13	-7.52
2011	30256.08	1599349	1.89	47.95
2012	17,801.47	1215914	1.46	-41.16
2013	35,785.86	1294825	2.76	101.03
2014	51,131.82	1753134	2.92	42.88
2015	91,951.18	2525614	3.64	79.83
2016	9,397.00	3116440	0.3	-89.78
2017	8,425.00	2827680	0.29	-10.34
2018	13,685.00	2888885	0.47	62.43
Total	387694.45	23108236	1.68	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

The Chemicals sector Includes chemicals, Paints and varnishes and Industrial gases. As a regarded to FDI inflow it is at seventh place after the automobile industry. The FDI inflow in chemical sector has been given in Table 7. There has been significant fluctuation in during this period. It has been gone up from 5380.66 million in the year 2000 to 91951.1 million in the year 2015 and decreased thereafter. The inflow of FDI in this sector has shown rising trend during this period despite heavy variation from year to year. However, its share in aggregate flow of FDI ranged between from 1.46 percent to 5.87 percent during the study period.

FDI in Trading Sector

The trading sector includes Cash & Carry Wholesale Trading e-commerce, single brand and multi brand retailing. The Cash & Carry Wholesale Trading/Wholesale Trading (including sourcing from MSEs) allowed 100% FDI under automatic route. The Cash & Carry Wholesale trading/Wholesale trading would mean sale of goods/merchandise to retailers, industrial, commercial, institutional or other professional business users or to other wholesalers and relate subordinated service providers. Wholesale trading would, accordingly, imply sales for the purpose of trade, business and profession, as opposed to sales for the purpose of personal consumption. The yardstick to determine whether the sale is wholesale or not would be the type of customers to whom the sale is made and not the size and volume of sales. Wholesale trading would include resale, processing and thereafter sale, bulk imports with export/ex-bonded warehouse business sales and B2B e-Commerce. The FDI in e-commerce is allowed 100 % FDI under automatic route. E-commerce activities refer to the activity of buying and selling by a company through the e-commerce platform. Such companies would engage only in Business to Business (B2B) e-commerce and not in retail trading, inter-alia implying that existing restrictions on FDI in domestic trading would be applicable to e-commerce as well. Similarly, in Single Brand product retail trading allowed 100 % FDI with automatic route up to 49%. Foreign Investment in Single Brand product retail trading is aimed at attracting investments in production and marketing improving the availability of such goods for the consumers, encouraging increased sourcing of goods from India, and enhancing competitiveness of Indian enterprises through access to global designs, technologies and management practices. In Multi Brand Retail Trading 51% FDI is allowed under government route. FDI in multi brand retail trading, in all products is permitted, subject to the conditions that Fresh agricultural produce, including fruits, vegetables, flowers, grains, pulses, fresh poultry, fishery and meat products, may be treated unbranded.

Table 8 FDI Inflows in Trading Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Trading	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	1239.79	1,04,411	1.19	
2001	2204.38	1,60,711	1.37	77.8
2002	1824.16	1,61,345	1.13	-17.25
2003	831.46	95,640	0.87	-54.42
2004	682.16	1,47,814	0.46	-17.96
2005	1257.67	1,92,707	0.65	84.37
2006	3,860.97	5,03,573	0.77	206.99
2007	23,141.85	6,54,950	3.53	499.38
2008	27,698.55	15,95,295	1.74	19.69
2009	31,843.74	13,09,799	2.43	14.97
2010	25,780.55	9,60,150	2.69	-19.04
2011	25,931.22	15,99,349	1.62	0.58
2012	33,712.80	12,15,914	2.77	30.01
2013	40,846.89	12,94,825	3.15	21.16
2014	1,74,613.39	17,53,134	9.96	327.48
2015	2,28,091.39	25,25,614	9.03	30.63
2016	15,721.00	3116440	0.5	-93.11
2017	28,078.00	2827680	0.99	78.60

2018	30,963.00	2888885	1.07	10.27
Total	6,98,322.97	231,08,236.00	3.02	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

The FDI inflow in the trading sector has been next to the chemical (other than fertilizers). The FDI inflow in this sector from 2000 to 2015 has been given in Table 8. Its gross FDI inflow share has been significant increase in trading sector. It has been increased from 1236.79 million in 2000 to 228091.39 million in 2015. It was moving at slow pace up to year 2006 and constituted a small volume. However, after the year 2006, FDI flow in this sector increased significantly particularly, in the years 2014 and 2015. Consequently, it is showing very high growth rate. The share of FDI inflow in trading sector ranged from 1 to 10 percent of total FDI inflow during this period. However, its share in total FDI inflow increased 1.62 percent in 2011 to 9.03 percent in 2015.

FDI in Power Sector

The Indian power system is the fifth largest in the world and most complex with an annual electricity production of 1,031 billion units (BU), it is among the top five power consumers across the globe, and the demand is expected to touch 1,900 BU by 2020. Growth in industrial activities, population, economy, prosperity and urbanisation along with rising per-capita energy consumption, has widened the gap of energy access in the country.¹⁸ According to the Ministry of Power, the total installed capacity of power is 181,558 MW in India. Out of this, state sector, Central sector and private sector contribute 83,314 MW, 56,573 MW and 41,672 MW respectively. The state electricity boards (SEBs) generate, transmit and distribute electricity in coordination with private/Centrally-owned generating companies or other relevant agencies. The Central Electricity Authority (CEA), constituted under the Electricity Supply Act 2003 is responsible for developing a sound, adequate and uniform policy for the control and utilisation of national power resources. It is also responsible for the techno-economic appraisal of the project reports for the proposed power plants, including those in the private sector. MNRE is responsible for developing renewable power, for which the funding agency is the Indian Renewable Energy Development Agency Ltd (IREDA). The Government of India has also constituted independent regulatory commissions in 22 states. Distribution reforms have been initiated with distribution being privatized in a few states such as Mumbai, Orissa and Delhi. According to industry experts, the total demand for electricity will be above 950,000 MW by 2030. Opportunities are coming up in power generation, transmission, distribution and equipment and servicing with capacity additions for power generation, captive power plants being set up, government promoting private sector participation in transmission and distribution, transmission projects being awarded on tariff-based bidding, privatization of distribution franchisees, scope for rural electrification, more focus on improving efficiency and introducing advanced technology and greater need for operational and maintenance services. Foreign direct investment (FDI) up to 100% is permitted under the automatic route for Generation and transmission of electric energy produced in hydroelectric, coal/lignite based thermal, and oil and gas based thermal power plants, Non-conventional energy generation and distribution, distribution of electric energy to households, industrial, commercial and other users. There is no requirement of licenses to set up new power plants, though FDI is not allowed in the nuclear segment. An income tax holiday for 10 years in the first 15 years of operation and waiver of capital goods, import duties on mega power projects, above 1,000 MW generation capacity is provided as incentive for investing in the sector. Power procurement is permitted through a transparent bidding process. There is no custom duty on the import of capital goods for mega power projects.

Under the Power Sector investment 49 % FDI & FII is permissible for Power Exchanges. FDI investment will be subject to the government approval. However, such foreign investment would be subject to FDI limit of 26% and FII limit of 23% of the paid-up capital, FII investments would be permitted under the automatic route and FDI would be permitted under the government approval route. FI purchases shall be restricted to secondary market only, No non-resident investor/entity, including persons acting in concert, will hold more than 5% of the equity in these companies and the foreign investment would be in compliance with SEBI Regulations.

Table 9 FDI Inflows in Power Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Power Sector	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	4840.17	104411	4.64	
2001	17411.75	160711	10.83	259.73
2002	31076.68	161345	19.26	78.48
2003	7418.51	95640	7.76	-76.13
2004	2,503.55	147814	1.69	-66.25
2005	1,513.45	192707	0.79	-39.55
2006	8,931.46	503573	1.77	490.14
2007	10,207.64	654950	1.56	14.29
2008	54,612.13	1595295	3.42	435.01
2009	75,582.23	1309799	5.77	38.4
2010	48,676.88	960150	5.07	-35.6
2011	78,393.75	1599349	4.9	61.05
2012	39,058.98	1215914	3.21	-50.18
2013	33,770.79	1294825	2.61	-13.54
2014	66,773.12	1753134	3.81	97.72
2015	50,097.23	2525614	1.98	-24.97
2016	7,473.00	3116440	0.23	-85.08
2017	10,473.00	2827680	0.37	40.14
2018	7,330.00	2888885	0.25	-30.01
Total	5,56,144.32	231,08,236.00	2.41	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

As regard to FDI inflow in the power sector, it is on eighth position. The FDI Inflow in power sector from January, 2000 to December, 2015 has been given in Table 9. The FDI inflow in power sector increased from 4840.17 million in 2000 to 50097.23 million 2015 and decreased in the year 2018 as 7,330 million. There has been wide variation in FDI flow in this sector from year to year. The share of inflow of FDI in power sector ranged from 0.79 percent to 19.26 percent of total FDI during this period. It was 19.26 percent in the year 2002 and it was merely 0.79 percent in the year 2005.

FDI in Hotel and Tourism

The travel and tourism sector are providing several socio-economic benefits like Provision of employment, income, foreign exchange and development of other sectors. In addition, investment

in infrastructural facilities such as transportation, accommodation/stay and other tourism related services lead to an overall development of infrastructure in the economy. According to the World Economic Forum’s Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Report 2013, India ranks 11th in Asia Pacific region and 65th globally out of 140 economies ranked on travel and tourism Competitiveness scale. India has witnessed steady growth in its travel and tourism sector over the past few years. Total tourist visits have increased at a rate of 16.3 percent annually, from 577 million tourists in 2008 to 1057 million tourists in 2012.

Table 10 FDI Inflows in Hotel and Tourism Sector with Percentage Share out of Total FDI from 2000 to 2018

Year	FDI in Hotel and Tourism Sector	Total FDI	% Share out of Total FDI	% Growth as Per Preceding Year
2000	524	104411	0.5	
2001	471.54	160711	0.29	-10.01
2002	2237.89	161345	1.39	374.59
2003	2594.21	95640	2.71	15.92
2004	1,527.23	147814	1.03	-41.13
2005	2,799.59	192707	1.45	83.31
2006	8,174.86	503573	1.62	192
2007	10,581.23	654950	1.62	29.44
2008	22,729.27	1595295	1.42	114.81
2009	28,885.39	1309799	2.21	27.08
2010	22,790.82	960150	2.37	-21.1
2011	41,933.66	1599349	2.62	83.99
2012	1,80,966.16	1215914	14.88	331.55
2013	22,320.33	1294825	1.72	-87.67
2014	48,652.88	1753134	2.78	117.98
2015	73,028.78	2525614	2.89	50.1
2016	87,610.00	3116440	2.81	19.97
2017	61,400.00	2827680	2.17	-29.92
2018	21,520.00	2888885	0.74	-64.95
Total	640747.84	23108236	2.77	

Source: Various Newsletters from 2000 to 2018

India’s tourism industry is experiencing a strong growth in high spending foreign tourists, and coordinated government campaign to promote “Incredible India”. Tourism has become a significant industry in Indian economy and is contributing around 5.9 per cent to the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and providing employment to about 41.8 million people. As per the World Travel & Tourism Council, the tourism industry in India is likely to generate US\$ 121.4 billion and Hospitality sector has the potential to earn US\$ 24 billion in foreign exchange by the year 2015. However, Indian hospitality industry has total of 110,000 rooms in India, as against a total requirement of approximately 250,000 demonstrating the available potential that continues to exist in this industry. On the other hand, India is requiring huge investment in the country for the infrastructure development in tourism and hospitality sector.

FDI inflow in the hotel and tourism has been given in Table 10. The hotel and tourism sector include hotels and restaurants, tourism and others Hotel & Tourism. The flow of FDI in this sector increased from 524 million in 2000 to Rs. 73028.78 million in 2015. It increased at an annual exponential growth rate of 34.7 percent. There has been wide variation in FDI inflow during this period. However, it is showing rising trend. High growth rate achieved in hotel and tourism sector has been mainly on account of relatively small inflow from the year 2000 to the year 2005. The share of FDI inflow in hotel and tourism sector ranged between from 0.29 percent to 2.89 percent during this period with one exception. It was 14.88 percent during 2012.

Conclusion

There are two routes of FDI inflow into India: Automatic Route (RBI Route) and Approval Route (FIPB Route). Besides, channel of allowing FDI, sectoral caps have also been put in place keeping in mind the nature of sectors and their current position vis-à-vis their foreign counterparts. Comprehensive Bilateral Agreement (CBA), Free Trade Area (FTA), Regional Comprehensive Economic Partnership (RCEP), Policy Forum (PF), Joint Ministerial Commission (JMC) and Working Group (WG) have been established or initiated with countries/groupings such as South East Asian nations, European Union, USA, Australia, China, and Brazil respectively to promote FDI into India and making way for Indian investments into these countries/groupings. As per the International Labour Organization (ILO) report on “Global Employment and Social Outlook: Trends 2015” job creation in the coming years will be mainly in the services sector. Indian Government has taken policy initiatives to promote services exports which include the Service Export from India Scheme (SEIS) and organizing Global Exhibition on Services (GES). But, due to imbalanced transformation of Indian Economy from Primary to Secondary & from Secondary to Tertiary, there is broad gap in manufacturing which is peculiar to India in particular, which is being addressed by the earlier governments and current Government via initiatives such as ‘Make in India’. Star performing sectors in terms of attracting FDI into India include Construction, Electronics, Information technology (viz. Computer Software), Telecommunications, and Drugs and Pharmaceutical. Automotive, Chemicals, Trading, Power and Hospitality sectors have the vast potential for FDI inflows and can be major contributors in terms of employment generation, creating value, supplementing infrastructure and providing support to India’s foreign trade by enhancing foreign exchange reserves. By looking at the trends of FDI, major sources of FDI is coming into sectors such as Services, Construction, Computer Hardware and Software, Telecommunications, Drugs and Pharmaceutical, Automotive, Chemicals, Trading, Power and Hospitality Sectors. And major contributors are Mauritius, Singapore, USA, UK, Japan, Cyprus, Netherland, Luxembourg, Russia, Germany and UAE. Major cities attracting FDI in India includes Mumbai, New Delhi, Bangalore, Chennai, Hyderabad, Ahmadabad and Kolkata.

References

1. Government of India, Ministry of Fiancé, Economic Survey 2014-15, p.112. <http://indiabudget.nic.in/es2014-15/echapvol2-07.pdf>.
2. Government of India, Ministry of Finance, Economic Survey 2015-16, Press Information Bureau, 26-February-2016, <http://pib.nic.in/newsite/PrintRelease>.
3. Sirari, Arjun Singh and Bohra Narendra Singh. (2011). “Foreign Direct Investment (FDI) in India Service Sector (A Study of Post Liberalisation)”, International Journal of Economic Research, Vol. 2, Issue 2, pp. 10-18.
4. Government of India, Ministry of Commerce, and industry Department of Industrial Policy Promotion, press note no 10, 2014(series) http://dipp.nic.in/English/acts_rules/Press_Notes/pn10_2014.pdf.

5. Kozul-Wright Zeljk and Howells Jeremy. (2002). Changing Dynamics of Global Computer Software and Services Industry: Implications for Developing Countries. United Nations Publications, Vol. 12.
6. Vijayasri V.G. (2013). Performance of India's Electronics & Computer Software Services Industry, Abhinav national Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Arts & Education, Vol. 2, Issue 6, pp. 58-73.
7. http://ficci.in/sector/39/project_docs/ficci_website_content-telecom.pdf.
8. Telecom Regulatory Authority of India. (2016). Quarterly Report December 2015, "The Indian Telecom Services Performance Indicators October-December, 2015. New Delhi, India http://www.trai.gov.in/WriteReadData/PIRReport/Documents/QPIR_Oct_to_Dec-15.pdf.
9. Gopika, G. G. (2014). Foreign Direct Investment Policies in the Liberalized Telecom Sector of India- A Review. International Journal of Business and Management Invention, Vol. 3, Issue 3, pp.01-08.
10. India Pharma Summit 2014-15: Policy Landscape Reforms for Strengthening Indian Pharmaceutical Industry, department of pharmaceutical, ministry of chemical and fertilizer, government of India" http://www.searo.who.int/india/mediacentre/events/2015/brochure_india_pharma_summit_2014-15.pdf.
11. Paul, Reeva. (2014). FDI in the Pharmaceutical Sector: Dampener or Booster? Gian Jyoti E-Journal, Vol. 4, Issue 1, pp.97-111.
12. Government of India. (2014)., Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Department of Industrial Policy and Promotion, Press Note No. 1, 2014 series, http://dipp.nic.in/English/acts_rules/Press_Notes/pn1_2014.pdf.
12. Rajan, Reshmi A. and Ravichandran N. (2014), "Effect of FDI Inflows in Indian Automobile Industry" International Journal of Scientific Research, Vol. 3, Issue 11, pp. 64-68.
13. Gupta Pankaj, Gupta Rajdeep and Maheshwari Pulkit. (2015) "A Review: Present Indian Automobile Industry." MIT International Journal of Mechanical Engineering, Vol. 5, Issue. 1, pp. 30-36.
14. http://ficci.in/sector/7/project_docs/chemical-petrochemical-sector.pdf.
15. Government of India. 2015). Ministry of Commerce and Industry, Department of Industrial Policy & Promotion, Consolidated FDI Policy, http://www.dipp.nic.in/English/Policies/FDI_Circular_2015.pdf.
16. Changing rules of Indian power sector: Empowering the economy, Confederation of Indian Industry, publication, 2015, pp.1. <https://www.pwc.in/assets/pdfs/publications/2015/changing-rules-of-indianpower-sector-empowering-the-economy.pdf>.
17. <http://www.investindia.gov.in/power-sector>.
18. Government of India, Ministry of Commerce & Industry, Department of Industrial Policy & Promotion Consolidated FDI Policy, http://dipp.nic.in/English/Policies/FDI_Circular_01_2013.pdf.
19. Ghosh, Jaideep. (2013). Travel and Tourism Sector: Potential, Opportunities and Enabling Framework for Sustainable Growth. An International Tourism Fest on Tourism and Hospitality, 5-7 December, 2013, Chandigarh India.